

Digital Social Touch Toolkit: a research tool for studying attitudes towards digital touch

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Abstract. We present the Digital Social Touch Toolkit, a research tool in development aimed at the systematic study of differences in attitudes regarding the ethics of digital social touch interactions. The toolkit consists of cards depicting digital touch interactions that participants should place on rating scales based on their attitude towards the scenario allowing for effective and efficient data gathering for quantitative research.

Keywords: Digital social touch · Haptic technology · Ethics · Card-based research toolkit

1 Introduction

Crucial to the experience of touch are the ethical aspects of consent, safety, agency, and trust [3]. Technological advances in areas such as virtual reality and artificial intelligence warrant the investigation of the ethics of digital social touch interactions (e.g., how to deal with physical harassment of an avatar in virtual reality [1]). The aim is to develop the Digital Social Touch Toolkit into a validated scientific instrument to study attitudes regarding digital social touch interaction between demographically different populations. This focus distinguishes our toolkit from those previously developed such as the card-based Designing Digital Touch toolkit [2] aimed at supporting designers of digitally mediated touch technologies. Moreover, in contrast to the touch-area maps developed to study allowed touch behavior at different body locations [4], this toolkit enables a more general way to systematically manipulate contextual factors important to touch interactions beyond body location.

2 Digital Social Touch Toolkit

The Digital Social Touch Toolkit is a research tool to systematically study differences in attitudes regarding the ethics of digital social touch. For example, between people of different cultures, ages, and genders. The toolkit consists of cards depicting scenarios in which a digital social touch interaction takes place. These scenarios can vary, among other things, in terms of technology (e.g., virtual reality, human-robot interaction, mediated touch), type of interaction (e.g., handshake, arm touch, hugging), and social context (e.g., at home or in public). Depending on the research question a set of cards can be created to study the relevant variables. Participants in the study will be instructed to sort the cards based on their attitude towards the scenarios on a Likert scale covering the dependent variable(s) of the research (e.g., ranging from 1: completely inappropriate to 5: completely appropriate).

Fig. 1. Example of scenario cards “embraced by a tele-operated robot controlled by <type of relationship (left to right): a salesperson, an acquaintance, a colleague, a friend, your partner> while you are at home” rated on level of appropriateness.

Here we illustrate how the toolkit can be used to address the following example research question: “Are there gender differences in the attitude towards being touched remotely by other people through a tele-operated robot?”. In such a study the effect of the independent variable (gender) on several dependent variables can be investigated (e.g., touch appropriateness, touch pleasantness, touch intrusiveness, requirement for consent before touching, feeling of social connectedness). A deck of scenario cards is required in which one variable is manipulated at a time, resulting in a systematic experimental design and reduced cognitive demand on the participants facilitating rapid sorting. In this example we choose the type of relationship (e.g., partner, mother, close friend, acquaintance, stranger) between the participant and the person controlling the tele-operated robot. The type of relationship is considered a moderator variable that is hypothesized to affect the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Figure 1 illustrates the placement of scenario cards on a

sorting template containing a 5-point Likert scale of levels of appropriateness. The same deck of scenario cards can be repeatedly sorted to collect ratings on different dependent variables. Moreover, additional decks can be included in the experiment which can be sorted on the same sorting templates to study the effects of other moderating variables (e.g., the social context in which the interaction takes place: at home vs. at work).

3 Future directions

The next step will be to evaluate the validity and reliability of the toolkit by conducting a study including participants from a wide range of demographical backgrounds to gain insight into its psychometric properties. Concurrent validity will be assessed through correlational analyses comparing the toolkit ratings to existing validated self-report questionnaires such as the Touch Experiences and Attitudes Questionnaire (TEAQ) [5]. In addition, we envision the development of several spin-off versions of the toolkit suitable for use-cases beyond quantitative research. For example, a version of the toolkit with more open-ended scenarios can facilitate discussions among the general public about digital touch etiquette. To increase the impact of the Digital Social Touch Toolkit we will provide open access to our finalized toolkit versions. Depending on the use-case a digital version (e.g., for conducting online studies or measuring response times in a controlled lab setting) or a physical toolkit (e.g., to facilitate a group discussion) might be more suitable.

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